

A STUDY OF PROBLEMS IN TEACHING OF CIVICS AT SECONDARY LEVEL

Dr.V.N.Patil

Director

School of Education

S.R.T.M.U. Nanded.

1.1 Introduction:

The subject of Civics is taught at secondary level in the title of Social science in Maharashtra. Social science includes History, Civics, Geography. It is found that teaching of Civics at secondary level is not easy as other school subjects. Though Civics is the subject of daily affairs, teacher and learner should have some of facilities. This study was an effort to make aware about present situation regarding with learning and teaching of Civics at secondary level.

1.2 Statement of the Problem:

“A Study of Problems in Learning & Teaching of Civics at Secondary Level”

1.3 Functional Definitions:

1. Secondary Level -

This school level includes 9th & 10th STD.

2. Civics -

A subject, which is recognized by MSCERT & Maharashtra State Bureau of Textbook Production and Curriculum Research, Pune for Secondary level.

3. Learning & Teaching -

Learning & Teaching of Civics at Secondary level.

4. Problems -

Problems related with Learning & Teaching of Civics.

1.4 Significance & Need of the Research:

If secondary student is introduced Civics primarily, he can become aware of various issues related with Civics. Civics is one of the important social sciences. It is the science which guides about our duties and rights. The student is emerging citizen. So that it is necessary for him to make aware of Civics. As this point of view, the subject of Civics is taught at secondary level in the title of Social science in Maharashtra. So it is needed and significant to know present situation and problems of learning and teaching of Civics.

1.5. Objectives:

1. To study problems of secondary teachers in Civics teaching at secondary level.
2. To study problems of secondary students in Civics learning.
3. To suggest solutions for easiness in learning and teaching of Civics

1.6.1 Scope:

1. The working area of research is Nanded city.
2. Learning and teaching process of Civics subject will be studied here.
3. The population of research is teachers & students of Civics at secondary schools. Sample was selected from above mentioned population. Only Marathi medium schools were considered in the research.
4. The research was completed with using survey method of research.

1.6.2 Limitations:

1. The results of the research were limited for Nanded city which is the district place in Maharashtra state.

1.7 Population:

All of students and teachers from secondary schools are the part of population.

1.8 Sample:

- i) 20 teachers who teach Civics at secondary level were selected as sample by using purposive sample method.
- ii) 20 students who learn Civics at secondary level were selected as sample by using purposive sample method.

1.9 Method of Research:

Survey method of research was used for proposed research.

1.10 Tools of Research:

Questionnaire was used for the research.

1.11 Statistical Parameters:

Percentage was used for the research.

1.12 Data analysis:

Teacher's views about teaching of Civics are collected through Questionnaire. Data analysis is given below:

Table No.1. Presentation of data collection about problems in teaching Civics:

Sr. No.	Question / Key words	Responses			
		1	2	3	4
1	Education in Civics or Political Science or Public Admn.	Graduate	Post Graduate	Other/ Diploma	Nil
		3	05	00	12
2	Special Training for teaching Civics	Yes	No	--	--
		1	19	--	--
3	Nature of Training for teaching Civics	1-2 days	7 days	More than week	--
		01	00	00	
4	Availability of reference books in Civics	5-10	10-15	15-20	More
		16	01	00	03
5	Number of Periods for Civics (weekly)	1-2	3-4	More	--
		18	01	01	

6	Problems in teaching Civics	Student's attitude	Lack of Preparation	Less of reference books	Less of knowledge
		16	--	04	--
7	Opinion about coordination bet'n syllabus of Civics & Daily life	Yes	No	--	--
		20	00	--	--
8	Availability of Teaching aids	Yes	No	--	--
		18	02	--	--
9	Cooperation of associate teachers	Yes	No	--	--
		20	00		
10	Expectations for teaching of Civics	Start from Prim.	Project Method	Nature of curricula	Development in Training
		03	04	01	12

Table No.2 Presentation of data collection about problems in learning Civics:

Sr. No.	Question / Key words	Responses			
		1	2	3	4
1	Do you face problems in learning of subject, Civics?	Yes	No	--	--
		17	03	--	--
2	Problems in learning of subject, Civics.	Class-Contro l	Teacher's attitude	Speed of teachi ng	Other
		03	00	14	03
3	Does teacher give Examples regarding to	Yes	No	--	--

	daily life in teaching?	11	09	--	--
4	Problem of failing to remember content due to examples given by teacher are out of textbook.	Yes	No	--	--
		02	18	--	--
5	Problem of Availability of reference books in Civics	Yes	No	--	--
		0	20	--	--
6	Interests in learning Civics	Yes	No	--	--
		17	03	--	--
7	Stress in learning Civics	Yes	No	--	--
		14	06	--	--
8	Actions in study of learning Civics out of classroom	Home work	Memorization	Self study	Other
		05	13	01	01
9	Student's cooperation in classroom process	Yes	No	--	--
		17	03		
10	Cooperation of students of 10 th std.(senior students)	Yes	No	--	--
		08	12	--	--

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1.13 Results:**A) Results from Teacher-Questionnaire:**

1. Mostly teachers of Civics have not completed any course in Civics or Political Science or Public Admn.
2. Special Training for teaching Civics was not completed by teachers of the Civics.
3. No any school has reference books of Civics in large amount.
4. The teachers have fewer Periods than they need for teaching Civics weekly according to school timetable.
5. Teachers have to face Student's attitude towards Civics as major Problem in teaching Civics. They mentioned that student is not serious in learning Civics as other subjects.
6. According to teachers, there is coordination bet's syllabus of Civics & Daily life.
7. Teachers are receiving Cooperation of associate teachers.

8. Teachers Expect Qualitative development and quantitative growth in trainings of teaching Civics.
9. A few Teachers expect that project method should be applied to teach Civics.
10. Civics should be taught from Primary education. It is expected by some of the teachers.
11. Very few teachers expect changes in nature of curriculum of Civics.

B) Results from Student-Questionnaire:

1. Maximum students are facing problems in learning of Civics.
2. Maximum speed of teaching is the major Problem in learning of subject of Civics.
3. Teacher gives Examples regarding to daily life in teaching Civics.
4. Students have no Problem of failing to remember content due to examples, which are out of textbook given by teacher.
6. Though Students have Interests in learning Civics they are experiencing Stress in learning Civics.
7. Mostly students choose memorization of the question-answers as the major action in study of Civics.
8. Maximum students cooperate in classroom process.
9. The amount of Cooperation of students of 10th std. (Upper level class) is neither maximum nor minimum it is just satisfactory (near about 60%).

1.14 Recommendations:

A) Recommendations for Teachers:

1. Teachers of Civics should complete any course in Civics as additional Degree, Diploma or Teaching Methodology etc.
2. Special Training for teaching Civics should be attended by teachers of the Civics in large amount.
3. Teacher should innovative practices in teaching Civics to make student's attitude more positive than present.
4. Teacher should keep attention towards his speed of teaching. It should not be too slow or too fast.

B) Recommendations for Students:

1. Though Students have burden of various subjects, activities, expectations of parents and teachers, they should make extra efforts like self-study etc. to make learning of Civics easy.

2. Students should practice Yoga or meditations for stress-management.
3. Students should choose way of consideration instead of memorization of the question-answers as the major action in study of Civics.

C) Recommendations for Schools:

1. Schools may have reference books of Civics in large amount.
2. Schools may have Teaching aids for teaching of Civics in large amount.
3. Schools should provide minimum three periods each class weekly for Civics.

D) Recommendations for various Institutions:

- 1) National Institutions like N.C.E.R.T. or N.C.T.E. should arrange crash courses for teachers of Civics.
- 2) State C.E.R.T.s should make efforts to provide various types of teaching aids and study material for teachers.
- 3) Extension Service centers should arrange Teacher Training Camps focusing on Civics teaching in large amount.

1.15 Topics for further research:

1. Innovative practices in Teaching and Learning of Civics.
2. Problems in Civics Education in rural India.

1.16 Conclusion:

In Conclusion it should be focused that Civics Teaching is essential today. It should be taken more seriously. There is need to discuss on various issues like evaluation, Teaching Models etc. at school level to state or national level.

1.17 References:

1. Best J.W., Khan J.V. Research in Education, Prentice Hall of India, New Delhi, Ninth Edition
2. Text Book of Civics for secondary level, MSBSE, Pune
3. Teaching”, Nutan publication,Pune.(5 june 1978)